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Isolation and Antibacterial Activity of Antibiotic-Producing Bacteria Recovered from Soil in Kano, Nigeria

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ABSTRACTS

Filamentous soil bacteria belonging to the genus *Streptomyces* are widely recognized as industrially important micro-organisms for their ability to produce secondary metabolites including antibiotics. The present study aimed at isolation and determination of antibacterial activity of antibiotic producing bacteria recovered from soil in Kano. Forty eight different soil samples were collected from Gwarzo, Katsina, Hadejia and Maiduguri roads. Twelve soil samples were collected from each of the four different sites and transported to Postgraduate Laboratory, Bayero University Kano for physical and microbiological analysis. The mean value of soil temperature, pH, moisture content and organic matter obtained are 26-27°C, 6.5-7.5, 43.4-46.9% and 18.9-19.8% respectively whereas the mean Streptomycetal count obtained is 1.46×10^6 - 1.53×10^6 cfu/g. The *Streptomyces* species isolated include: *Actinomadura*, *Nocardia*, *Actinomyces* and *Streptomyces* and were tested against clinical bacterial isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*. The metabolites extracted and tested were found to be of broad spectrum that inhibited the growth of both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria with zones of inhibition up to 31mm. Thin layer chromatography of the extracts ranged from 0.67-0.78 Retention Factor and infrared spectrum revealed how much functional groups were absorbed at each transmittance, the position, shape and intensity of the peaks were analyzed in the spectrum. The investigation demonstrate that strains of antibiotic-producing bacteria are present in the soil of Kano Metropolis, Nigeria and these could be harnessed by the pharmaceutical industries for the production of antibiotics from local sources.

Keywords: Isolation; Antibacterial activity; *Streptomyces*; Soil.

1. INTRODUCTION

Serious infections caused by bacteria that are resistant to commonly used antibiotics have become a major global health care problem in the 21st century. Many strains of bacteria have acquired resistant and in many cases multi-resistant to therapeutic agents, thus, rendering these drugs ineffective as treatment of choice for infections caused by these pathogens (Alanis, 2005).

Secondary metabolites specifically antibiotics produced by microorganisms have been very useful for the cure of certain human diseases caused by bacteria, fungi and protozoa. Most of antibiotic producers used today are soil microbes with fungal strains, streptomyces and bacteria being extensively used in industrial antibiotic production (Satvinder, 2014).

Filamentous soil bacteria belonging to the genus *Streptomyces* are widely recognized as industrially important micro-organisms because of their ability to produce many kinds of novel secondary metabolites including antibiotics. Of all known drugs, 70% have been isolated from bacteria (actinomycetes) of which 75% and 60% are used in medicine and agriculture respectively while 20% are isolated from fungi and 10% from eubacteria (Miyadoh, 1993; Makuta and Owolewa, 2011).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was carried out at four different areas in Kano State which included Gwarzo road (site A), Katsina road (site B), Hadejia road (site C) and Maiduguri road (site D).

Sample collection

Forty eight (48) soil samples were collected from four different areas of Kano namely: Gwarzo (site A), Katsina (site B), Hadejia (site C) and Maiduguri roads (site D). The samples were taken at a depth of 10cm (around plant roots) in a sterile polythene bags using soil auger and sterilized spatula (Bahing, 2008). Aseptically, it was taken to Postgraduate Laboratory, Bayero University Kano for analysis.

Physico-chemical analysis

The soil samples temperature and Ph were determined using mercury – in – glass thermometer and pH meter (Pye Model 292) respectively while percentage moisture and organic contents were determined according to procedures described by Gliessman (1998). This was repeated and the average was recorded

Isolation of Streptomyces species from the soil samples

Actinomycetes from the soil had been isolated using pour plate technique on Starch Casein Agar (SCA) after serial dilution in distilled water. Using sterilized pipette, 0.1ml aliquots of each dilution was aseptically transferred into each of the corresponding labeled petridishes. Fifteen ml of prepared SCA was poured into each petridish within 15 minutes of original dilution and was carefully mixed by swirling. It was then allowed to solidify. The prepared dishes were inverted and incubated at room temperature for 7 days and were observed for colonies appearance. Petridishes containing 30-300 colonies were counted and recorded in colony forming unit per gram of soil (cfu/g). Actinomycete isolates were purified by streak –plate technique and were preserved in SCA slant at 4°C (Rana and Salam 2014).

Extraction of Metabolites

The selected isolates were cultured in starch casein broth and incubated at 30°C for 7 days. Actinomycetes cultures were filtered and then Antibacterial compound was recovered by solvent extraction method as described by (Liu *et al.*, 1995). Ethyl acetate was added to the filtrate in the ratio 1:1[v/v] and incubated for 1hr for complete extraction. The ethyl acetate phase that contains an antibiotic agent was separated from aqueous phase. The precipitate was dissolved in minimum amount of ethyl acetate, this is the actual metabolite and was used on the clinical bacterial isolates and its activities were determined.

Characterization of Metabolites

Actinomycetes were characterized morphologically. Phenotypic characters such as aerial mass, colour, pigmentation, spore chain morphology and Gram staining characteristics were observed using x100 objectives. The observed characters were compared with Berger's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology and then the organisms were identified by Starch hydrolysis, casein hydrolysis, urease, catalase, motility tests and acid fast characteristics as described by Cheesbrough (2010).

Antibacterial Activity of Metabolites

Primary screening of streptomyces isolate was done by perpendicular streak method on nutrient agar plates.

The test organisms used are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Eschericia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonea* and *Proteus mirabilis*. Each were streaked as a straight line on nutrient agar medium and incubated at 30°C for 7 days. After 7th day different strains of bacteria were streaked at right angle but not touching each other and then incubated at 32°C for 24hours. Organisms that are susceptible to the antibiotic compound produced by *Streptomyces* did not grow near the *Streptomyces*. Finally, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of the extract were determined using the tube dilution method (Rana and Salam 2014).

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) and Spectroscopy

TLC and infrared spectrum were performed and the retention factors and molecular structure of metabolites were determined (Paula, 2009).

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Mean Physico-chemical analysis of the Soil

Parameter	A	B	C	D
Temperature (°C)	26.20	25.60	25.80	26.50
pH	6.5	6.7	7.6	6.9
Moisture content (%)	45.8	46.9	43.4	46.8
Organic matter (%)	19.8	19.9	18.9	19.4

Table 2: Mean *Streptomyces* Count

Sample Site	Mean <i>streptomycetal</i> Count (cfu/g)
A	1.48 X 10 ⁶
B	1.46 X 10 ⁶
C	1.49 X 10 ⁶
D	1.53 X 10 ⁶

Table 3: Morphological and Cultural Characteristics of *Streptomyces*

Characteristics	Isolates 1	Isolates 2	Isolates 3	Isolates 4
Colony shape	Flat	Straight	Branch	Flat
Colour	Ash	Green	White	Waxy
Spore formation	+	+	+	+
Cell morphology	Cocci	Long rod shape	Rod Y and V shape	Cocci
Inference	<i>Actinomadura</i> (micromono spore)	<i>Nocardia</i>	<i>Actinomyces</i>	<i>Streptomyces</i>

Table 4: Biochemical Characteristics of *Streptomyces*

Characteristics	Isolates 1	Isolates 2	Isolates 3	Isolates 4
Acid fast staining	-	-	-	-
Casein test	+	+	+	+
Urease test	+	+	+	+
Catalase test	-	-	-	-
Starch hydrolysis	+	+	+	+
Gram reaction	+	+	+	+
Motility	Non motile	Non motile	Non motile	Non motile

+ = Positive reaction

- = Negative reaction

Table 5: Antibacterial Activity of Metabolites

Clinical bacterial isolates	Concentration (ml)	Zone of Inhibitions (mm)			
		1	2	3	4
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.5	19	10	21	12
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	0.5	0	12	0	0
<i>Salmonella typhae</i>	0.5	12	8	6	13
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	0.5	0	0	0	31
<i>Pseudomonas acenginosa</i>	0.5	7	0	6	12
<i>E. coli</i>	0.5	12	14	6	14

Table 6: Thin Layer Chromatography

Extracts	Retention Factor (cm)
1	0.73
2	0.78
3	0.71
4	0.67

4. DISCUSSION

The result of the physicochemical parameters shows no significant difference in terms of temperature, moisture- content and organic matter contents ($P > 0.05$). This is in line with the finding of Borodina *et al.* (2005) which found no significance in the parameters.

The results of morphological characteristics of the isolates indicated that the purified isolates of actinomycetes belong to *streptomyces* species as they showed good sporulation with compact, chalk – like dry colonies of different color variations from pink to white color. The isolates showed branched mycelium in their cell morphology similar to fungal character.

The biochemical characterization indicated that pigment production was very well observed in most of the *streptomyces* species. They are all Gram positive, all the isolates were efficient in hydrolyzing starch, casein, urease and catalase. This is also in agreement with the work of (Borodina *et al.*, 2005).

The mean *streptomyces* count indicated no significant difference, the P value was 0.9509 which is greater than 0.05. This is in accordance with the work of (Stackebrandt, 1991).

Streptomyces species having broad spectrum of antibacterial activity are of major importance for their study in the isolation of the novel antimicrobial compound. The metabolites extracted from the *streptomyces* inhibited the growth of both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria with zones of inhibition up to 31mm.. The P value is also considered no significant.

Thin layer chromatography revealed four extracts yielded with Retention factors (RF) ranged from 0.67-0.78 which is in accordance with the work of (Sihem, 2011). The result of infrared spectrum revealed how much energy was absorbed at each transmittance. The position, shape and intensity of the peaks were analysed in the spectrum.

The result of the analysis is performed by the Agilent Technologies which are presented in graphs.

5. CONCLUSION

The four *Streptomyces* isolated from the soil in Kano metropolis are the common *Streptomyces*. The physico-chemical parameters were favored for the growth of three organisms. All the organisms have significant potential for the production of the metabolite which has inhibited the growth of clinical isolates. The metabolite was found to be broad spectrum that inhibited the growth of both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the major findings in this research the four *streptomyces* isolates should be employed in the large scale production of antibiotics, so as to increase the economy of the Kano State government and its indigenes in general. It will help to eradicate many pathogenic microorganisms; this will uplift the health condition of the people.

Further studies should be conducted to extract pure form of the antibacterial agent which requires a series of purifications process and different chemical analysis such as High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography.

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